

DEFINING OPTIMAL CRITERIA TO INITIATE GnRH ANTAGONIST IN FLEXIBLE ANTAGONIST ICSI CYCLES

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Abstract

Background:

This study was on infertile women who were experiencing ICSI procedure with flexible antagonist protocol aiming to help in determining optimal criteria to start antagonist inhibition for patients having rapid growth of follicles, or those with increased levels of estradiol E2, since, criteria when to initiate GnRH antagonist administration differ usually, The criteria chosen in this study were based on a collected information about reproductive physiology and also records from previous researches, hence, size of leading follicle, level of serum estradiol and also, serum LH level were used in current study to start antagonist administration, pregnancy rates were evaluated according to these various criteria.

Materials and Methods: One hundred twenty infertile females were subjected to ICSI flexible antagonist protocol at the High Institute for Infertility Diagnosis and Assisted Reproductive Technologies/Al-Nahrain University from October 2020 to April 2022, inclusion standards were fresh transfer cycles and frozen cycles excluded also. Those patients were randomized in to three groups according to the criterion they justified to begin the antagonist, Group A: 40 patients where the antagonist was started when the leading follicle size was (12-14). Group B: 40 patients where the antagonist was started when the serum E2 was exceeding 500pg/ml and group C: 40 patients where the antagonist was started when the serum LH level > 5 IU/l. those patients were subjected to controlled ovarian hyper-stimulation using the flexible GnRH-antagonist protocol. Data were analyzed by (SPSS) version 26.0 using χ^2 , t-test, ANOVA, Fisher exact tests.

Results: no significant difference in mean age among the three studied groups ($p = 0.275$), No significant difference among the three groups concerning the duration of infertility p value equal to (0.899). Regarding the type of infertility there were no significant differences among the three studied groups ($p=0.163$), there was also no statistical difference among the study groups concerning the cause of infertility ($p=0.064$). while there was significant difference in body mass index (BMI) among group A, B and C groups with p value equal to (0.022) with lowest value in group B (25.30 ± 2.93).. comparable basal hormonal levels of the study groups except for LH level, there was significant difference ($p=0.049$), also, a highly significant difference in LH levels among study groups at starting day of antagonist $p < 0.001$, furthermore, concerning data obtained at antagonist starting day, the difference was significant regarding the E2 levels $P= 0.017$, with higher

levels of E2 and LH in group C, total gonadotropin dose among the three studied groups did not reach statistical significance, there was significant difference in the cycle day of antagonist initiation ($p=0.022$) and the initiation was earlier in group A 6.65 ± 1.33 , There was no significant difference in the duration of stimulation (days) and in number of antagonist ampoules total number of follicles at antagonist time was comparable a highly significant difference seen when the leading follicle size (LFS= 15) and (LFS= 16). While regarding day of ovulation trigger, the mean serum concentration of E2 and progesterone were comparable between the three time, However, mean serum concentration of LH was higher in group C with highly significant value (p value= 0.001), no significant difference among the three study groups regarding other stimulation characteristics. The difference was highly significant ($P= <0.001$) in pregnancy rate among the three different groups seen with highest percentage being in the B group 22(55%).

Keywords: Flexible GnRH antagonist protocol, criteria of antagonist initiation, lead follicle size, serum estradiol and Luteinizing hormone levels, pregnancy rates.

Objectives:

Determining optimal criteria for initiating GnRH antagonist aim to prevent LH surge based on lead follicle size, serum E2 and LH levels and evaluate the pregnancy rates in these different groups.

Conclusion: This study reveals that counting on only one criteria to start antagonist, that was the leading follicle size may lead to earlier start, more number of ampoules used that may interfere with endometrial receptivity and more coast, this study suggests an algorithm of the three criteria to make a decision that is individualized for each patient to achieve better outcome. Furthermore; considering serum estradiol as an adjuvant criterion to decide antagonist administration was significantly correlated to pregnancy.

Introduction:

Intracytoplasmic sperm injection broadly recognized as a successful management for infertility most causes (Broqua et al., 2002).^[1] Gonadotropin-releasing hormone (GnRH) antagonist protocols mainly used in the recent years in assisted reproductive technologies (ART), act by blocking the release of luteinizing hormone (LH) besides the follicle-stimulating hormone (FSH) from the pituitary gland by competitive inhibition (Peiwen et al., 2016). Criteria as when to establish antagonist inhibition during flexible antagonist protocols are likewise not standardized. However; cycle day, size of leading follicle, and serum E2 levels were used and criteria vary within each parameter (Brianna et al., 2018).

Lower rates of clinical pregnancy in antagonist protocol is not coincidental as concluded by the American Society for Reproductive Medicine in 2016 and also, Cochrane review, besides further studies are required to decide the best time of GnRH-antagonist inhibition during IVF cycles (Al-Inany et al., 2001). Previous literatures stated that the LH surge may not occur before the leading follicle reached a diameter of 15 mm and/or also, serum E2 reached the level of 600 pg/l (Lainas et al., 2005). serum E2 exceeds 600 pg/ml was further suggestion to start GnRH antagonist (Frydman et al., 1991). For that, the first criterion chosen when the leading follicle size was 12-14 mm in diameter and the second one involving the E2 serum levels above the value of 500pg/ml. As for the third criteria serum LH of > 5 IU/L is

used to decide whether or not to start antagonist inhibition based on also data from physiological facts and also from results of previous literatures where, several researches have concluded that serum LH levels must be between 1.2 and 5.0 IU/L for better follicular growth (Liu et al., 2019), also other researchers hypothesized that some patients with serum LH level that is low, less than 4 IU/L during COS may have no LH surge (Luo et al., 2021, Lv et al., 2021, Liu et al., 2019). Choosing the third criterion based likewise on viewpoints attained by recurrent LH measurements during COS.

2. Materials and methods

One hundred twenty infertile females were subjected to ICSI flexible antagonist protocol at the High Institute for Infertility Diagnosis and Assisted Reproductive Technologies/Al-Nahrain University from October 2020 to April 2022, Ethical approval of the present study was issued by the Local Medical Ethical Committee of the High Institute for Infertility Diagnosis and Assisted Reproductive Technologies, Al-Nahrain University, inclusion standards were fresh transfer cycles and frozen cycles excluded also. Those patients were randomized in to three groups according to the criterion they justified to begin the antagonist, Group A: 40 patients where the antagonist was started when the leading follicle size was (12-14). Group B: 40 patients where the antagonist was started when the serum E2 was exceeding 500pg/ml and group C: 40 patients where the antagonist was started when the serum LH level > 5 IU/l. those patients were subjected to controlled ovarian hyper-stimulation using the flexible GnRH-antagonist protocol.

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FSH 75 IU FSH activity/ampule) regular fixed daily subcutaneous injection with doses depended on the BMI, age of women, previous response to ovulation induction and AFC. based on the patient's individualities, follicular development, and provided that LH levels not exceeding 10 IU/l, HMG (Menogone) 75IU (Ferring, GmbH/ Germany) was added. Pituitary inhibition was accomplished with a flexible GnRH antagonist protocol when the criterion that was set according to their group was met. 0.25 mg cetrorelix acetate (Cetrotide[®], Merck Serono, Geneva, Switzerland). Triggering of final oocyte maturation was made with recombinant HCG with two ampoules Ovitrelle[®] 250µg subcutaneous injection (Ovitrelle[®], Merck Serono) once at least three leading follicles reach 17-18, followed by ovum retrieval 35-36 hours later. The morphological assessment of the oocytes retrieved and embryos was done in the ICSI laboratory of the "High Institute for Infertility Diagnosis and Assisted Reproductive Technologies", for 2 hours after retrieval the cumulus oocytes complexes were incubated. afterward, the meiotic status of aspirated oocytes was assessed following the denudation by using hyaluronidase enzyme and mechanical pipetting. the presence of an extruded first polar body (IPB) in the perivitelline space (PVS) and the absence of a germinal vesicle (GV) oocyte are used as indicators of nuclear maturity (MII oocyte). The intracytoplasmic sperm injection (ICSI) technique was done. Fertilization assessment and pronuclear evaluation were achieved 16–18 hours after sperm injection. The presence of two pronuclear and two polar bodies characterized normal fertilization. Yet, scoring of cleavage-stage embryos was based on the Istanbul consensus workshop (ASRM and ESHRE Special Interest Group of Embryology, 2011) and were classified into grade I, II, and III. Embryo transfer was done at day 3 where grade one embryos (fragmentation < 10% and an even blastomere). The luteal phase was supported from the day of oocytes aspiration vaginal progesterone (Cyclogest[®] 400 mg twice: Cox Pharmaceuticals, Barnstaple, UK). Serum β-HCG analysis carried out on day 14 following the embryo transfer to reveal biochemical pregnancy.

Data were entered and analyzed by using Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS) software program version 26. All categorical variables were presented by frequency and percentages while numerical continuous variables were represented by mean (a measure of central tendency) and standard deviation (a measure of dispersion). Association between categorical variables was assessed by the Chi-Square test or Fisher's Exact Test (if > 20% of expected cell counts are less than 5) accordingly. The difference between means of numerical variables was tested by the One-way ANOVA test and independent samples t-test according to the number of involved groups. Considering P-value equal to or less than 0.05 as a significant.

3. Results

The mean age and BMI of the study groups were demonstrated in table (1), there was no significant difference in mean age among the three studied groups ($p = 0.275$) while there was significant difference in body mass index (BMI) among group A, B and C groups with p value equal to (0.022) with lowest value in group B (25.30 ± 2.93). No significant difference among the three groups concerning the duration of infertility p value equal to (0.899). Regarding the type of infertility there were no significant differences among the three studied groups ($p=0.163$), there was also no statistical difference among the study groups concerning the cause of infertility ($p=0.064$).

Table (1): comparison of infertility features among the study groups

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P-value
Quantitative	(Mean ± Standard Deviation)			(One-way ANOVA test)
Age	31.8±5.39	31.4±5.20	29.93± 5.78	0.275
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.88±2.85	25.30±2.9325	26.95±3.11	0.022
Duration of infertility	7.78±4.53	8.16±3.83	7.79±4.38	0.899
Qualitative	Number (percentage)			P-value
Type of infertility				
Primary	35(37.2%)	31(33.0%)	28(29.8%)	0.163 (Chi-Square test)
Secondary	5(19.2%)	9(34.6%)	12(46.2%)	
Causes of infertility				
Male factor (MF)	11(25%)	22(50%)	11(25%)	0.064 (Fisher's Exact Test)
Female factors	18(41.9%)	11(25.6%)	14(32.6%)	
Unexplained	4(50%)	2(25%)	2(25%)	
Combined	7(28%)	5(20%)	13(52%)	

SD: Standard deviation, BMI: Body mass index, *: p value ≤ 0.05 (significant).

Basal hormonal levels of the study groups were illustrated in table (2), there was significant difference regarding LH level (p=0.049) while there was no significant difference regarding FSH level (p=0.260), prolactin level (p=0.977), E2 (p=0.306), TSH (p=0.466) and Progesterone (P=0.055), also there were no significant difference in antral Follicle Count (p=0.558).

Table (2): Comparison of Antral Follicle Count and basal hormonal levels among the study groups

	Group A	Group B	Group C	P-value (One-way ANOVA test)
	(Mean ± Standard Deviation)			

Basal FSH (mIU/ml)	6.20 ± 1.56	5.50 ± 2.15	6.05 ± 1.87	0.260
Basal LH (mIU/ml)	4.92 ± 1.79	4.52 ± 1.80	5.55 ± 2.00	0.049
Basal Prolactin (mIU/ml)	15.00 ± 5.91	15.14 ± 6.84	14.82 ± 6.49	0.977
Basal TSH (mIU/ml)	2.18 ± 0.84	1.96 ± 0.81	2.01 ± 0.85	0.466
Basal Progesterone (ng/ml)	0.54 ± 0.21	0.45 ± 0.17	0.55 ± 0.20	0.055
Basal E2 (pg/ml)	41.78 ± 11.38	40.11 ± 8.92	43.72 ± 10.83	0.306
AFC (count)	14.05 ± 7.53	13.90 ± 3.68	15.23 ± 6.11	0.558

FSH: Follicle stimulating hormone; LH: Luteinizing hormone; TSH: Thyroid stimulating hormone; E2: Estradiol, AFC: Antral Follicle Count *: p value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

LH and E2 levels at starting day of antagonist shown in table (3). the results showed a highly significant difference in LH levels among study groups (4.05 ± 2.1, 4.21 ± 1.92, 6.19 ± 1.66, p < 0.001) and also the difference was significant regarding the E2 levels (626.19 ± 533.27, 557.32 ± 42.60, 830.84 ± 534.42, P = 0.017) among the A, B, C groups respectively, with higher levels of E2 and LH in group C.

Table (3): Comparison of LH and E2 levels at antagonist starting day among the study groups.

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P-value (One-way ANOVA test)
	(Mean ± Standard Deviation)			
Antagonist starting day LH (mIU/ml)	4.05 ± 2.1	4.21 ± 1.92	6.19 ± 1.66	<0.001*
Antagonist starting day E2 (pg/ml)	626.19 ± 533.27	557.32 ± 42.60	830.84 ± 534.42	0.017*

LH: Luteinizing hormone; E2: Estradiol*: p value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

Table (4) shows a comparison of total gonadotropin dose among the three studied groups, this difference did not reach statistical significance ($p= 0.585$). As for the comparison of total menogone (HMG) dose (IU) after antagonist day there was also no significant difference among the study groups ($p= 0.933$).

Table (4): Comparison of Total GT dose (IU) and Total (HMG) dose after antagonist starting day (IU)

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P-value (One-way ANOVA test)
	Mean \pm Standard Deviation (Minimum-Maximum)			
Total GT dose (IU)	1558.38 \pm 505.56 (760-2850)	1564.30 \pm 411.11 (900-2400)	1673.73 \pm 717.11 (900-3450)	0.585
Total (HMG) dose after antagonist starting day (IU)	155.63 \pm 242.21 (0-750)	161.25 \pm 245.86 (0-900)	167.25 \pm 280.90 (0-1200)	0.933

*: p value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

Table (5) compare the cycle day of antagonist initiation and duration of stimulation (days) among study groups, as the table shows there was significant difference in the cycle day of antagonist initiation ($p= 0.022$) and the initiation was earlier in group A 6.65 ± 1.33 while in the B and C groups were 7.38 ± 1.35 and 7.30 ± 1.11 respectively. There was no significant difference in the duration of stimulation (days) among study groups ($p=0.267$) with shortest duration was in the A group 8.55 ± 1.60 and a range of (5-11), there were no significant differences in number of antagonist ampoules among study groups ($P= 0.336$) but however; groups A and C having patients taken more than 5 ampoules, while the maximum number of antagonist ampoules used by the patients in the B group was 5 ampoules. Table (6) demonstrate that the total number of follicles at antagonist time was comparable among study groups ($p= 0.900$), the same table shows also no statistical differences regarding follicular size when the leading follicle size was ≤ 11 and leading follicle size that is equal to (12-14) among study groups while a highly significant difference seen when the leading follicle size (LFS= 15) and (LFS= 16) with highest value being among group B (1.23 ± 1.40) and (0.60 ± 1.19) respectively ($p < 0.001$).

Table (5) Comparison of Cycle day of antagonist initiation, Duration of stimulation (days) and Number of antagonists' ampoules among study group

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P-value (One-way ANOVA)
	Mean ± Standard Deviation (Minimum-Maximum)			
Cycle day of antagonist starting	6.65 ± 1.33 (4-10)	7.38 ± 1.35 (5-10)	7.30 ± 1.11 (5-10)	0.022*
Duration of stimulation (days)	8.55 ± 1.60 (5-11)	9.05 ± 1.55 (6-12)	9.00 ± 1.35 (6-12)	0.267
Number of antagonists' ampoules	3.98 ± 1.34 (2-7)	3.63 ± 0.83 (2-5)	3.73 ± 1.01 (2-7)	0.336

*, p

value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

Table (6) Comparison of Total number of follicles and leading follicle size at antagonist starting day

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P-value (One-way ANOVA test)
	(Mean ± Standard Deviation)			
Total number of follicles at antagonist time	14.28 ± 7.98	14.70 ± 5.59	14.95 ± 6.08	0.900
LFS ≤ 11	5.38 ± 3.68	4.05 ± 2.78	3.93 ± 3.22	0.091
LFS= (12-14)	8.68 ± 7.10	8.82 ± 7.10	10.35 ± 5.81	0.364
LFS=15	0.00 ± 0.00	1.23 ± 1.40	0.68 ± 1.14	<0.001
LFS=16	0.00 ± 0.00	0.60 ± 1.19	0.05 ± 0.31	<0.001

*, p value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

The mean serum concentration of E2 and progesterone were comparable between the three time points at ovulation trigger day (p= 0.085) table (7). However, mean serum concentration of LH was higher in group C as compared to the other two groups with highly significant value (p value= 0.001).

Table (7) Comparison of Hormones' Profile on the Day of Ovulation Trigger

Trigger hormones	Group A	Group B	Group C	P-value (One-way ANOVA test)
	(Mean ± Standard Deviation)			
Trigger day E2	1233.17± 796.67	1314.46 ±463.31	1574.75±817.11	0.085
Trigger day LH	1.37± 0.86	1.47 ± 0.75	2.05 ± 0.87	0.001 *
Trigger day Progesteron	1.32± 0.41	1.54± 2.12	1.49± 0.40	0.724

LH: Luteinizing hormone; E2: Estradiol. *: p value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

*: p value ≤ 0.05 (significant)

There were no significant differences among the three study groups regarding other stimulation characteristics as shown in tables (8 and 9),

Table (8): Comparison of oocytes characteristics among the study groups

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P-value (One-way ANOVA test)
	(Mean ± Standard Deviation)			
Oocytes number	10.25 ± 6.86	10.75 ± 4.71	10.80 ± 5.29	0.892
Metaphase I (MI)	1.23 ± 1.42	1.60 ± 1.73	1.25 ± 1.61	0.504
Metaphase II (MII)	7.23 ± 5.90	7.38 ± 3.58	7.28 ± 4.50	0.990
Germinal vesicle (GV)	1.10 ± 1.35	0.90± 1.33	0.85 ± 1.25	0.668
Abnormal	0.33 ± 0.69	0.60 ± 1.15	0.78 ± 1.14	0.142
Raptured	0.35 ± 0.7	0.35 ± 0.66	0.53 ± 0.75	0.454
Degenerated	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.05±0.31	0.371

Empty	0.05±0.31	0.00±0.00	0.00±0.00	0.371
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SD:

Standard deviation; *: p value $0 \leq .05$ (significant)

Table (9): Comparison of Number of fertilized oocyte, Number of good quality embryos and Number of embryos transferred among the study groups

Variables	Group A	Group B	Group C	P-value (One-way ANOVA test)
	(Mean ± Standard Deviation)			
Number of fertilized oocytes	6.13 ± 4.64 (1-15)	6.85 ± 3.01 (2-15)	6.35 ± 4.13 (0-20)	0.708
Number of good quality embryos	3.33± 2.40 (0-9)	4.13 ± 1.89 (1-9)	3.70± 2.57 (0-9)	0.304
Number of transferred embryos	2.38 ± 1.19 (0-4)	2.95 ± 0.93 (1-4)	2.48± 1.26 (0-4)	0.058

SD: Standard deviation; *: p value $0 \leq .05$ (significant)

The rate of pregnancy among patients enrolled in the current study is shown in table (10 with highly significant difference ($P = <0.001$) in pregnancy rate among the three different groups seen with highest percentage being in the B group 22(55%)

Table (10): pregnancy rate among the study groups

Pregnancy test	Groups No. (%)			Total	P-value
	A	B	C		
Negative	37(92.5%)	18(45%)	38(95%)	93(77.5%)	<0.001* (Chi-square test)
Positive	3(7.5%)	22(55%)	2(5%)	27(22.5%)	

SD: Standard deviation; *: p value $0 \leq .05$ (significant)

DISCUSSION

there was significant difference in body mass index (BMI) among the study groups. Zhu et al (2022) stated that too low or too high BMI was a potential hazard for infertility in women (Zhu et al., 2022) and it was agreed with this study that it preferred to maintain more suitable BMI levels in women preparing for pregnancy, yet, this statistical difference was within criteria to be included

in this study that is a BMI within (18-30 kg/m²), Basal hormonal levels and antral follicular count (AFC) of patients involved in the current study were comparable between the three study groups as there was no significant difference regarding antral follicle count, since this was one of the requirements for participating in the study, as patients with abnormal basal hormonal levels were excluded. But however; current study disagreed by Lainas et al, 2005 observed significant differences in the basal FSH and E₂ values, furthermore Anaya et al. (2018) shown that statistical difference in E₂ levels amongst studied groups. In this study, significant difference regarding LH level (p=0.049) was observed with highest value was in the serum LH group, but however, it was within the accepted normal bounds to be enrolled in the ICSI trial.

Regarding antagonist starting day the LH levels among study groups there was a highly statistical difference with (p< 0.001) and also significant difference regarding the E₂ levels (P= 0.017) with higher levels of E₂ and LH in group C. Other studies revealed that endogenous LH levels directly affected by GnRH antagonists, and are related to oocyte growth and COS consequences and it is thought that LH levels throughout COS must be evaluated for best ART outcome (Chen et al., 2016). Urman and colleague in 2018 stated that the significance of an LH surge without an associated elevation in progesterone is controversial. So, the revealing of an isolated LH surge in the GnRH antagonist cycles is less likely to change management of the cycle. (Urman et al., 2018). However; Lainas et al in 2005 stated other opinion, that earlier start of antagonist can increase IVF outcome by controlling LH surge in patients with more rapid response (Lainas et al., 2005). And other hypothesized that elevated LH levels during the follicular phase correspond with detrimental outcomes regarding natural and stimulated cycles (Ozturk et al., 2017). In Group B, a value exceeding 500 pg/ml chosen as a level for E₂ to start the antagonist for this it was lower than group A and C.

Since LH level > 5 was chosen to start the inhibition in the third group, the mean LH level was higher than the other two groups with high level of significance accompanied with elevated mean serum E₂ level in an also significant manner this agreed by many studies, since LH can stimulate the proliferation and also, differentiation of theca cells to secrete androgen, and synergistically enhance estrogen production (Judith et al., 2005). Other researchers assumed that small amounts of progesterone were produced with LH helps, and by this, encouraging positive feedback of estrogen, that is essential for follicular growth and maturation (Hattori et al., 2018). So, it obvious that the increment in LH level goes hand by hand with elevation in serum E₂ levels. While the antagonist was started when LH levels were more than 5 IU/L in the C group of patients and despite the accompanying elevated E₂ level, there were no canceled cycles due to over stimulation and were capable to escape the LH surge, and the outcomes were not poorly affected, so an individualized initiation day for supplementation of the antagonist may support an optimal ovarian response, and this mostly real for patients who are hyper responders. Total gonadotropin dose among the three studied groups and total menogone (HMG) dose (IU) after antagonist starting day show no statistical significance, a tailored approach to ovarian stimulation may result in optimum outcomes as it is hypothesized by (Shoham et al., 2018). Earlier in this study the ovarian

stimulation was with rFSH only but however; some patients show sub optimal follicular growth and there was a need to add LH after the day of antagonist possibly because GnRH antagonist administration leads to rapid decline in Plasma LH levels that may affect follicular growth and maturation. Many authors postulated the beneficial role of LH, Bosch et al in 2018 stated that LH promote steroid synthesis in granulosa cells, inducing the maturation of the oocyte up to the metaphase II state, inducing the production of proteases, and playing a special role in the ovulation and induction of luteinization, (Bosch et al., 2018). The additional FSH and, mainly, LH administration during the conventional ovarian stimulation was hypothesized by Detti et al., to correct the drug's adverse effects (Detti et al., 2008). A study in 2005 conducted that women with elevated basal LH levels such as PCOS or women with diminished ovarian reserve may be more liable to higher variation (decreases) in LH levels and by depending on the LH level and level of progesterone suppression throughout antagonist inhibition, some women may get advantage from modification of the GnRH antagonist dose or supplement of LH (Judith et al., 2005). there was significant difference in the cycle day of antagonist initiation ($p= 0.022$) and the initiation was earlier in group A, although there were no significant differences in number of antagonist ampoules among study groups ($P= 0.703$), but however; the A group having five patients used more than 5 ampoules compared to only two patients in the C group while the maximum number of antagonist ampoules used by the patients in the B group was 5 ampoules, so this study reveals that counting on only one criteria to start antagonist, that was the leading follicle size leads to earlier start more number of ampoules used that may interfere with endometrial receptivity and more coast. And this was agreed by Ozturk and co-workers in 2017 as they suggested that an early initiation of GnRH antagonist administration seemed to be more cost-effective compared to a late initiation of GnRH antagonist administration, the same was theorized by (Inal et al., 2018 and Wertheimer et al., 2020). Al-Obaidi M, in 2022 stated that the day of antagonist initiation whether before or after day 6 of controlled hyper stimulation has no effect on assisted reproductive outcomes although, the duration of stimulation was shorter with statistically significant difference and less total dose of gonadotropin required when antagonist started before 6 days of stimulation (Al-Obaidi M, 2022). A study by Tannus et al., stated that a significant number of patients on a flexible GnRH antagonist start begin antagonist supplementation after day 6 of the cycle. Despite various stimulation and laboratory features, it does not adversely affect the reproductive result as compared with earlier initiation of GnRH antagonist (Tannus et al., 2013). The duration of stimulation (days) was comparable among study groups ($p= 0.933$) with shortest duration was in the A group. Same results seen by many other studies (Luo et al., 2021, Liu et al., 2019, Hattori et al., 2018, Judith et al., 2005). However; in other study, shorter duration of stimulation shows that the application of the flexible protocol improves the infamous benefits of the GnRH antagonists. (Lainas et al., 2005). The total number of follicles at antagonist time was comparable among study groups ($p= 0.900$), this was predicted since patients included were nearly comparable in their basal characteristics like age and AFC. No statistical differences regarding follicular size when the leading follicle size was ≤ 11 and leading follicle size that is equal to (12-14) among study groups while a highly significant difference seen when the leading follicle size (LFS= 15)

and (LFS= 16) with highest value being among B group, since group A started the antagonist when leading follicle size is equal to (12-14) so this group having no follicles =15 or 16 this leads to the highly significant difference seen. A subgroup of patients was recognized by Kolibianiki et al, in 2003 with no leading follicle of ≥ 15 mm on cycle day 6 of stimulation and therefore, they established the GnRH antagonist at a later period in the follicular phase, also, hypothesized that elevated E_2 and LH levels with also, a delayed administration of GnRH antagonist caused the negative consequence on reproductive outcome, due to prolong exposure of the endometrium to the E_2 and LH (Kolibianiki et al., 2003), unlike Kolibianiki's other study found that patients with elevated E_2 had better pregnancy outcome than patients with lower E_2 exposure. (Mochtar, 2004). The latest edition of Textbook of Assisted Reproductive Techniques stated that in a flexible start of GnRH antagonist, it was administered only after presence of certain endocrine and/or also, sonographic criteria signifying that a risk for a LH rise might be present besides these criteria have varied amongst researches (Gardner et al, 2018), and the criteria when to start the antagonist was the interest of many researchers, In some studies, GnRH antagonist was started when the leading follicle reached 14 mm of size (Esinler, 2014). Others had the antagonists initiation when the size of leading follicle was at 12 mm (Kolibianakis et al., 2011). Still, some other studies considered serum E_2 and LH level regardless the leading follicle size. Serum E_2 level above 600 pg/ml and also, LH serum level exceeding 10 IU/l considered by Lainas in 2005 as further criteria, then this study followed by numerous studies, Orvieto et al. and Kaur et al. initiated the antagonists' after the serum estradiol levels were above 400 pg/mL, and/or also, follicles reached 14 mm in diameter (Yang et al, 2016). In consequence to these conflicting studies, this study suggests an algorithm of the three criteria to make a decision that is individualized for each patient to achieve better outcome.

Regarding ovulation trigger day, the mean serum concentration of E_2 was comparable between the three groups ($p= 0.085$) with higher value in group C. This may be related to higher level of LH and total number of follicles in same group and in the same time limit, since as stated by Huirne et al., LH is requisite for production of progesterone via granulosa cells luteinization likewise estradiol is synthesized by androstendione production as estradiol substrate. Hence, in GnRH antagonist protocols LH levels were correlated to progesterone and also, to estradiol (Huirne et al., 2004). Also, mean serum concentration of LH was higher in group C as compared to the other two groups with highly significant value (p value= 0.001), as this group basal and antagonist starting day level was higher than the other two groups. Previous studies indicated that profound LH inhibition is unfavorable for patients subjected to GnRH agonist or GnRH antagonist ICSI cycles (Shi et al., 2018, Chen et al., 2016). Urman et al in 2018 hypothesized that serum LH levels regular monitoring seems to be unnecessary throughout stimulation cycles, neither to define an endogenous LH surge during GnRH antagonist cycles, since LH levels rapidly decrease after starting GnRH antagonist and nor to certify pituitary down-regulation in the long GnRH agonist protocol, (Urman et al., 2018). On the other hand, serum level of progesterone was higher on the B group compared to group A and group C, but with no significant difference ($p= 0.724$). As the total progesterone levels are related to the absolute volume of luteinized granulosa cells, hence,

absolute number of follicles can reflect the total levels of progesterone on the hCG trigger day (Judith et al., 2005) and since the total number of follicles was lowest in group A, it corresponds the lowest value of progesterone, even so with-out significant difference. This may have an agreement with Wei study who reported that the progesterone level on hCG trigger day might have a little effect on clinical pregnancy (Wei et al., 2015). There was no significant difference among the three study groups regarding other stimulation characteristics as shown in tables (8 and 9), this may be attributed to the comparable patient's characteristics and nearly comparable basal and trigger day hormonal profile among the three study groups. groups this may be attributed to the comparable patient's characteristics and nearly comparable basal and trigger day hormonal profile among the three study groups. However; there was a trend towards higher number of retrieved oocyte in group B where there was higher level of E₂, as it was also clarified by Siddhartha et al. that higher E₂ levels on the day of ovulation trigger would predict increased oocyte yield after controlled ovarian hyper stimulation (Siddhartha et al., 2016). This may be attributed to higher bulk of granulosa cells. Peña et al hypothesized that the serum E₂ level reflects the maturity of the follicle and the quality of the oocytes, and consider that highly elevated E₂ levels are not harmful to fertilization rates, oocyte quality, and cleavage of embryo. These studies also propose that continued supra physiological E₂ levels resulting from ovarian hyper stimulation have no detrimental effects on the quality of growing oocytes and also, quality of embryos (Peña et al 2002), although, there was somewhat higher number of good quality embryos and transferred embryos in group B in this study where the E₂ level was less than group C but however; more than group A. Yang et al, hypothesized that the high level of progesterone on HCG trigger day can disturb the endometrial receptivity more than the quality of oocyte or embryo (Yang et al., 2015).

A highly significant difference ($P = <0.001$) in pregnancy rate among the three different groups seen with highest percentage being in the B group 22(55%). As was illustrated earlier group (B) was with more acceptable hormonal milieu at antagonist and trigger days compared to other two groups, where group (A) having lower LH and E₂ of trigger day that may interfere with follicular development and endometrial receptivity where it was thinner in this group in both time limits, also group(C) having higher LH and more supraphysiological level of E₂ that may cause excessive leutinization of granulosa cells and more mature endometrium, even so some characteristics, seemed to be optimal for clinical and ongoing pregnancy rates were existing in group (B) like lower number of antagonist ampoules, also, a trend of higher mean values of number of fertilized oocyte, number of good quality embryos and number of transferred embryos in group (B). However; there are many other factors influence pregnancy rates, as suggested by Luo et al. as corpus luteum function or endometrium receptivity may be effected by low serum LH levels throughout COS, and this can lead to the asynchrony concerning the embryo and the endometrium, hypothetically resulting in failure of implantation and hence, poor pregnancy outcomes (Luo et al., 2021). Even so, some other factors, like P, E₂, LH on the HCG trigger day, and also, age and BMI, might affect treatment consequences as stated by (Wang et al in 2017), It that quality of oocyte and the embryo besides endometrial receptivity has been shown to be most significant factors interfering with success of in vitro fertilization (IVF) (Wang et al., 2017).

Conclusion: This study reveals that counting on only one criteria to start antagonist, that was the leading follicle size may lead to earlier start, more number of ampoules used that may interfere with endometrial receptivity and more coast, this study suggests an algorithm of the three criteria to make a decision that is individualized for each patient to achieve better outcome. Furthermore; assessing Serum estradiol as an adjuvant criterion to decide antagonist administration was significantly correlated to pregnancy.

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Author Contribution

Muhammad SM, performed the study, examined and reviewed results, and manuscript writing with the help and supervision of LA Al-Anbari, and S Muayad

Conflict of Interest

The author declares no conflict of interest.

Ethical Clearance

The study was approved by the Ethical Approval Committee.

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